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INJURIOUS SPEECH AS A NARRATIVE DEVICE: PERLOCUTIONARY EFFECTS IN HORROR DISCOURSE

Our research explores injurious speech in horror discourse through speech act theory, focusing on its perlocutionary dimension and narrative function. Drawing on Austin's concept of perlocutionary effect, the study argues that utterances that inflict psychological, emotional, or symbolic harm operate not merely as characterising elements but also as structural devices that generate and intensify fear within the narrative. Injurious speech in horror texts – manifested in threats, dehumanising address, curses, and verbal degradation – produces anticipatory tension and destabilises fictional identities, thereby shaping the reader's emotional response. The paper emphasises that perlocutionary effects in horror are aesthetically modelled and strategically embedded, differing from everyday communication to enhance narrative tension and emotional engagement, raising questions about their specific narrative functions for the audience.

The theoretical framework of this study builds upon previous research on passionate discourse (A. Greimas), proximation theory (P. Cap), and critical approaches to hateful discourse (R. Wodak, J. Butler).

The research hypothesis can be described in the following statements:

1. Texts of horror discourse are emotionally charged and rely on the axiological opposition of the good and the bad. This opposition is not evident in non-conventional texts where the source of fear is not culturally, historically or socially stigmatised in society. In such texts, for the passion (fear) to appear, the subjects need to go through the stage of modalisation, or the final acquisition of traits of the bearers of this or that passion; moreover, the subjects should become clearly marked as active or passive participants of the passionate relations (Greimas & Fontanille, 1993).

2. Strategically, the process of modalisation contributes to the narrative development as it either mitigates the controversy or raises the degree of passionate opposition or creates suspense and unpredictability.

3. Discursively, the stage of modalisation in a horror narrative fits the characteristics of hateful discourse in public, political or social life when the speakers organise their speeches around the opposition WE VS THEY, ascribing all positive features to US and all negative ones to THEM. Even more, the closer THEY are, the more frightened WE should be (Cap, 2013).

4. Narratively, the rivalry of the sources of fear and their recipients in horror texts needs gradual explication for the narration to unroll logically and smoothly. Among other techniques that help its materialisation is the verbal expression of

injurious speech of (predominantly) fear recipients. To better understand this point, we suggest considering the hate-speech intensity scale, which classifies harmful rhetoric in public discourse (Bahador, 2020). The author draws a chain of the degrees of verbal injuries from disagreement, focusing on the opponent's hostile actions and characteristics, to the incitement to violence and death.

5. Logically, the hate-speech intensity scale entirely correlates with the recipient's of fear perception of the axiologically new for him world of horror: first, he sees that it is strange (it causes disagreement), later he identifies the negative differences in actions and features of the supposedly neutral objects, then these objects acquire non-human abilities, and finally the rivalry turns into the life or death stand. The destabilisation of the fictional identities of both the source and the recipient of fear marks the turning point in the narration, making it a text of horror discourse.

6. Pragmatically, injurious speech in horror discourse differs from real-life verbal aggression: it does not primarily aim at humiliating the addressee or asserting dominance. Rather, it intensifies affective involvement, fostering empathy and heightening emotional tension.

7. Narratively and perlocutionarily, such speech performs a structuring function. It symbolically reconfigures the opposition between the source and the recipient of fear, mobilises the fictional "US" against "THEM," and triggers a re-evaluation of the narrative world's axiological order. This axiological destabilisation becomes the decisive moment in the unfolding of horror discourse.

Consequently, the perlocutionary dimension of injurious speech emerges as an effective narrative principle in horror discourse, where verbal harm is reconfigured into an aesthetic and structural device that organises fear and redefines the axiological order of the fictional world.

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